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Perceptions, Efficiency, and Challenges of Implementing Koha- ILS in Academic Libraries of Pakistan: A Librarians' Overview

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine librarians' ability, efficiency and challenges related to KOHA (Integrated Library System) in Pakistan. The study used a quantitative research design employing a survey method. A Questionnaire was prepared, reviewed by experts, and shared with N=300 Librarians in Pakistan. Only 222 (74%) completed and returned the questionnaire. The data were analyzed using SPSS (27 v). Descriptive statistics, such as independent-samples t-tests and ANOVA, were used for data analysis. The findings show that the majority of librarians in Pakistan preferred KOHA-ILS for automation purposes, and perceive it as state of the art solutions for all kind of libraries; however, a few barriers like operating systems, technical issues, expert training, Lack of Automation knowledge, and poor technological tools are crucial issues; with these recommendations, Koha was marked as a tested software by the library professionals in Pakistan. The present research contributes meaningful guidance and evidence-based insights to scholars, librarians, policymakers, and organizational stakeholders in Pakistan and beyond.

Keywords: *"Koha library software, KOHA-ILS, Open Source Library System, Academic libraries, Library Management System, University libraries, Pakistan"*

Introduction

The rapid advancements of information technology have transformed the world into a global village. This transformation has influenced almost every aspect of human life. For all humans, information has become a vital factor for performing everyday academic and professional tasks. In an academic environment, information technology has enabled continuous access to information and improved its systematic management. Libraries were among the earliest adopters of information technology to enhance service delivery and operational efficiency. Thus, academic libraries had to adopt new automation technologies to create, organize, and access information beyond the four walls. In this context, information technology has enabled continuous access to information and improved its systematic management. Libraries, since the emergence of new technologies, have become knowledge-intensive institutions (Hussain, 2020). In Pakistan, library automation has gradually emerged as a critical component of modern library management, particularly in academic libraries (Mahmood Malik, 1996). In academic libraries, the integration of ICT has significantly improved the speed, accuracy and effectiveness of information processing and dissemination (Abid, 2021). The automation process and ICT facilitate the management of large volumes of bibliographic and user data in a more structured and efficient manner. Libraries increasingly rely on automated processes, reflecting a global shift toward technology-driven library operations. Library automation has improved acquisition, serial control, cataloguing, circulation, and reporting systems of contemporary libraries (Hussain & Rafiq, 2024). As a result, the adoption of library management software has become central to library automation initiatives. Library automation refers to the application of ICT systems to replace manual library operations with integrated, computerized workflows. Over time, library software has evolved into a powerful tool for transforming libraries from traditional to automated, electronic, digital, and virtual environments (Omeluzor et al., 2012). The past few decades have witnessed a substantial increase in the availability and use of library automation software, both in proprietary and open-source solutions (Iqbal et al., 2023). Within this evolving landscape, integrated library systems (ILS) such as Koha have gained prominence due to their flexibility, cost-effectiveness, and suitability for academic libraries in developing countries. Consequently, librarians and information professionals play a pivotal role in effectively managing and delivering library resources through such automated systems (Mairaj & El-Hadi, 2012). Koha is the most

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functionally complex open-source ILS available today, and its advanced capabilities are based on this foundation (Noor, 2022). "The name KOHA is derived from a Maori word that means 'gift' or 'donation.'" The development of KOHA began in 1999, with funding from a group of rural New Zealand libraries that considered proprietary software to be too expensive and lacking some capabilities (Sharma, 2021). Since its original implementation in 1999, thousands of libraries worldwide have adopted Koha functionality, each adding features and functions depending on the system's capabilities. With the release of Koha 3.0 in 2005, which included the powerful Zebra indexing engine, Koha became a viable, scalable option for libraries of all types. Katipo Communications Limited created the full-featured KOHA in New Zealand and implemented it in January 2000 for Horowhenua Library Trust. KOHA is meant to run on a small amount of hardware (Uzomba et al., 2015). According to Singh & Sanaman (2012), Koha is an "Open source" application, free software that contains the source code and allows users to change it to meet their library's needs. It also gives you the freedom to distribute it without restriction. An increasing number of libraries worldwide are steering Koha's development. Individually or collectively, these libraries support the creation of new features to aid their procedures (Jabeen, 2024). Koha's impressive feature continues to grow and expand to meet the needs of the libraries that sponsor it. Librarians may modify Koha library software to fit their specific workflow needs by selecting and choosing features through system settings management.

There is an assumption that libraries worldwide prefer proprietary systems. However, the case of developing countries like Pakistan is very different (Hussain & Rafiq, 2024). Research by Mairaj & Mukaram (2024) found that in Pakistan, numerous software are currently adopted for library automation; these include INMAGIC, CDS/ISIS, Foxpro, LAMP, Kitabdar, Dbase, Evergreen, Virtua, Libmax, KOHA, etc. Due to limited budgets for library automation, most libraries are adopting open-source software (OSS). Among them, the use of KOHA (ILS) software received widespread recognition. Financial constraints in developing-country libraries affect the adoption of proprietary systems. Consequently, libraries are now seeking alternative automation software, and the solution is Open-Source Technology. There needs to be a better understanding of the use of open-source systems in Pakistan, particularly in relation to KOHA (Asim & Mairaj, 2019). In their study, Hussain & Rafiq (2024) noted that selecting appropriate software for library automation is a crucial step that requires sufficient knowledge of available software and their capabilities before deployment in libraries. In their study, they opined that in Pakistan, numerous open-source software have been utilized to develop library services more efficiently than ever before. Common examples of this software include KOHA (ILS) and SLIMS. The present study was conducted to indicate the gap between KOHA (ILS) and the librarian's opinion. This study examined librarians' perceptions of KOHA, its efficiency in library automation, and the barriers they face while adopting it in their respective libraries. The present study will fill a gap in understanding librarians' awareness of technology and the barriers to adopting KOHA-ILS in their libraries.

Literature Review

Technology is evolving at an exponential pace, making it increasingly difficult for individuals to stay informed about emerging technologies. Hussain (2020) found that technological advancement could be observed across almost all sectors, including health centres, commerce, defence, and educational institutions, in this competitive world. The library has been a driving force in innovative technologies since the invention of the computer; it remained an early adopter of business applications during the mid-1960s. Numerous libraries have developed computerized circulation control systems based on batch-processing techniques (Mairaj & Mukaram, 2024). In their paper (Hussain & Rafiq, 2024), they opined that library automation began in Europe and America in 1930, when punch card equipment was introduced. In his study, Mahmood (1999) postulated that in Pakistan, the process of Library automation

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took place in the years 1980 -87. Adopting computer technologies is the first step toward automating library records.

Similarly, Mahmood (1996) confirmed that numerous library automation packages were used in Pakistan during 1990-2000. Some popular software for automation processes adopted during this era included FoxPro, DBase, LIMS, INMAGIC, Pak Library Software, Kitabdar, Virtua, and KOHA. (Khan et al., 2016) reported that in 2000, the Idea of OSS took hold worldwide, and libraries began automating with open-source software. Librarians in both advanced and developing countries have positive perceptions of OSS. The study further revealed that KOHA is a well-developed OSS for library automation, and many libraries in developing countries with limited budgets are adopting it. The Koha ILS was the first open-source library system and is considered one of the most reliable automation systems. Koha has many features, which is why librarians worldwide recommend it for their library operations.

Kumar V & Jasimudeen (2012) found that in India, more than 95.5% of libraries used KOHA-ILS and other open-source software, while only 18.4% used proprietary, commercial software. In their research, Khan et al. (2016) reported that the Government College University (GCU) libraries in Lahore have migrated their data from the Library Management System (LMS) to KOHA-ILS. The study found that the LMS software they were using was non-MARC and non-Unicode, and did not support the Urdu typeface, even though the GCU libraries held over 100,000 volumes in Urdu. As a result, at a meeting, the library staff agreed to use the Koha ILS software. Mamatlepa & Maluleka (2024) conducted a case study on the deployment of Koha ILS at the Deutsche Schule Charlotte in the United States, reporting that the library chose Koha for its rapid check-in, checkout, and inventory control systems. Their study of Siddique & Mahmood (2015) further clarified that only a few studies have been conducted on the use of KOHA-ILS, which offer limited information and discuss it only.

A study by Yang & Hofmann (2010) compared the OPACs of three software packages: Evergreen, Voyager, and KOHA. The study revealed that Voyager and Evergreen software are suitable for journal holdings; however, KOHA was linked to the ProQuest database to provide faceted search navigation. The study approved that KOHA was more efficient than the other two software. Similarly, in a study, Singh & Sanaman (2012), who found that Koha has more features than NewGenLib, compared Koha and NewGenLib. Shoeb & Rahman (2020) investigated open-source library solutions and found that KOHA offers a broader range of modules than ABCD and other related software. In a study, Choi (2023) evaluated KOHA, Evergreen, and OSS against other proprietary software and found that KOHA and Evergreen have more powerful modules than the other software. Yang & Hofmann (2010) compared KOHA with NewGenLib and found that KOHA offers more extensive modules than NewGenLib. According to Asim & Mairaj (2019), Koha software has grown in popularity and is the best option for library automation. Because of its free availability, the availability of required features, its worldwide client base, and universal access to information, libraries have embraced Koha as an ILS. According to Hussain & Jan (2018), the shift from conventional to technology-based library services has become easier and more cost-effective since the introduction of KOHA and other Open-Source Software, enabling more efficient service delivery.

Jabeen (2024) conducted a quantitative study among university librarians in Pakistan and revealed that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and facilitation conditions positively influenced librarians' intention to adopt KOHA in their respective libraries. Khan et al. (2016) reported that KOHA was first used in Pakistan in 2006. Khan & Ayesha (2022) reported that KOHA – ILS is increasingly adopted in Pakistani libraries due to its user-friendly modules. In their study, Asim & Mairaj (2018) found that Koha possessed all functions and features. However, academic librarians in Pakistan are still fearful of its installation for many reasons, such as the Linux Operating System, data migration, Z39.50, etc. However, KOHA is one of the most commendable software solutions, free of cost and open source. It was

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introduced in 1999. Hence, its use is increasing at an alarming rate despite its popularity, and KOHA use is manageable (Masrek et al., 2022). In a study, Asim & Mairaj (2019) found that Koha possessed all functions and features. However, academic librarians in Pakistan are still wary of its installation for many reasons, including the Linux Operating System, Z39.50 data migration, etc. Mohideen et al. (2019) conducted a study and found that librarians are facing several problems while implementing KOHA software in academic libraries as a new version of this software requires Linux based operating system, and the majority of the librarians are not familiar with this operating system; similarly the study of Hussain & Rafiq (2024) also found inadequate technical competencies, data transferring, and advanced operating systems are few challenges faced by the librarians while implementing them in BRAC University library. The research of Khan & Ayesha (2022) reveals a practical and systematic approach to modernization project implementation, beginning with project proposals, funding release, vendor selection, mode of procurement, workforce selection, selection of ILS (Koha) and LMS solution to the library's day-to-day activities, and a series of communications with the funding organization for library system automation. Kumar V & Jasimudeen (2012) found that untrained staff, funding shortages, and librarians' lack of interest are significant issues in implementing Koha Integrated Library Solutions. The study of Siddique & Mahmood (2015) discovered that librarians in Pakistan are not fully aware of modern technology. Despite the available literature in both regional and international contexts, no empirical studies were conducted in the context of Pakistan to examine the academic librarians' perception towards KOHA-ILS, its efficiency, and the challenges they face while adopting Koha in their academic libraries. There is still a research gap. The purpose of this study is to fill the gap in both theory and practice. The study offers insightful and evidence-based analysis and is useful for librarians, policymakers, stakeholders, and academia who intend to adopt KOHA-ILS as automation software in academic libraries in the future.

Research Methodology:

The study employed a survey method within a quantitative research design. A questionnaire was developed based on prior studies of (Asim & Mairaj, 2018; Wahidah et al., 2019; Alikoba & Lwanga, 2019). The initial draft was refined through feedback from research scholars in Pakistan. The experts who contributed research and used KOHA practically were targeted. The finalized questionnaire was pasted online via Google Forms for data collection. To ensure reliability and validity, a pilot test was conducted with 30 librarians who were not part of the main study. The research adopted a simple random sampling approach, targeting a population of N=300 librarians across various provinces of Pakistan. Contact details were gathered from Pakistan's library software directory. The survey targeted librarians using Koha-ILS, with invitations sent via email and WhatsApp. The survey was conducted among 300 librarians and it was active from September 10, 2025, to December 4, 2025. Of these 300 individuals, 76 responses were collected initially; follow-up reminders increased participation to 229 responses, and 7 were excluded due to incomplete information, resulting in 222 valid responses (74% response rate). Data were coded in Microsoft Excel and then exported to SPSS 26.0 for analysis. Descriptive statistics, independent sample t-tests, and ANOVA were employed for the analysis of the findings.

The objective of research:

The present study addressed the following objectives.

1. To explore librarians' perceptions regarding the adoption and usability of Koha-ILS in academic libraries across Pakistan.
2. To evaluate the efficiency and effectiveness of Koha-ILS in enhancing library operations and services in academic libraries in Pakistan.

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3. To identify and analyze the challenges faced by librarians during the implementation and ongoing use of Koha-ILS in academic libraries in Pakistan.

Research Questions

The study answered the following questions.

1. What are the perceptions of librarians in academic libraries in Pakistan regarding the adoption and use of Koha-ILS?
2. How does the implementation of Koha-ILS influence the efficiency and effectiveness of library operations in Pakistan's academic libraries?
3. What are the key challenges librarians in Pakistan's academic libraries faced during the implementation and usage of Koha-ILS?

Findings

The demographic information in Table I indicates that 139 (62.6%) respondents were male, while only 83 (37.4%) were female. This ratio indicates that the majority of them are male and use Koha in their respective libraries. The age distribution shows that 90 (40.5%) respondents were aged 30 or younger, while 64 (28.8%) were aged 31-40. The study also reveals that among 222 respondents, the majority, 153 (68.9%), are from public sector universities, while only 69 (31.1%) are from private sector universities. As for the qualifications of respondents, 9 (4.1%) were PhD holders, 52 (23.4%) held MS/MPhil degrees, 112 (50.5%) held MLIS/MA degrees, and only 49 (22.1%) held BS LIS Degrees. The respondent rate across Pakistan's provinces shows that the majority, 81 (36.5%), are from Punjab. The result also reveals that Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is second after Punjab, with 57 (25.7%), while 36 (16.2%) belong to Sindh province. The respondents from the Islamabad Capital Territory numbered 36 (16.2%), while only 3 librarians responded from Gilgit Baltistan (1.4%). Overall, the study reveals that Institutions in Punjab are numerous, and the lowest in the region is Gilgit Baltistan. It shows that librarians in Gilgit Baltistan have limited libraries that use Koha- ILS software.

Table 1: Demographic Information of Respondents

		<i>f</i>	Valid Percent
Gender	Male	139	62.6
	Female	83	37.4
Age	< 30	90	40.5
	31-40	64	28.8
	41-50	54	24.3
	>50	14	6.3
Qualifications	BS LIS	49	22.1
	MLISc/MA	112	50.5
	MS/MPhil	52	23.4
	PhD	9	4.1
Types of Organisations	Public Sector	153	68.9
	Private Sector	69	31.1
Designation	Chief Librarian	62	27.9
	Librarian	137	61.7
	Assistant Librarian	15	6.8
	Library Assistant	8	3.6
Experience in Years	1-5 Years	40	18.0

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	6-10 Years	75	33.8
	11-15 Years	62	27.9
	16-20 Years	33	14.9
	More than 20 Years	12	5.4
Provincial-Wise Distributions	Punjab	81	36.5
	Sindh	36	16.2
	KPK	57	25.7
	Baluchistan	9	4.1
	Islamabad	36	16.2
	Gilgit Baltistan	3	1.4
	Total	222	100

Table 2 shows the significant factors statements with $p < 0.05$ values from independent-samples t-tests; the results indicate that each statement highlights significant factors in Koha, with meaningful differences between male and female librarians, as indicated by the stereographic signs. Factors with $p > 0.05$, such as dependability, are not significant based on this analysis. Considered significant based on this analysis. Each statement shows the significant factors of academic librarians towards Koha-ILS, except "I find Koha dependable Male (Mean=3.36, SD=1.171), Female (Mean=3.11, SD=.884) and t-test significant, 2-tailed is .069.

Table 2: Perception of Librarians towards Koha-ILS: Data distribution based on male and female with t-test

No	Statements	Male Librarians (n=139)		Female Librarians (n=83)		t-test sig. 2-tailed	F test value
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
1.	Our Library Services are impacted by Koha software	3.53	1.426	2.77	1.253	.000*	6.135
2.	Charging and discharging of books are made easy by the use of Koha	3.69	1.191	3.24	.878	.001*	15.656
3.	Libraries have reached the next level because of Koha	3.66	1.183	2.99	.994	.000*	9.130
4.	Koha makes the acquisition system for smaller libraries simple	3.49	1.151	2.99	.876	.000*	27.858
5.	Koha also makes the union catalogue facility available	3.41	1.128	2.83	.998	.000*	4.668
6.	Koha makes me satisfied while carrying out library services	3.40	1.153	2.99	.819	.002*	30.292
7.	I would recommend Koha to other libraries	3.32	1.251	2.96	.943	.018*	22.122
8.	I find Koha dependable	3.36	1.171	3.11	.884	.069	19.901
9.	Koha greatly increases job productivity	3.45	1.149	3.02	.950	.003*	12.854
10.	Every function of an integrated library management software can be performed on Koha.	3.43	1.234	3.10	.919	.022*	23.146

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11.	Koha software is user-friendly	3.48	1.132	2.87	.866	.000*	15.805
12.	For efficient library services, Koha is consistent	3.44	1.155	3.07	.973	.012*	9.797

Table 3 presents academic librarians' perceptions of Koha based on qualifications, using ANOVA. The scholars apply the ANOVA test to four qualification groups (BS LIS, MLIS, MPhil/MS, and PhD). The result shows that all statements were found insignificant based on p-values 0.05, except the one "Every function of an integrated library management software can be performed on Koha" with (F = 4.595, p = .004). This statement shows significant differences across the qualification levels. Librarians with BS LIS degrees have the highest mean score towards KOHA across multiple statements (M=3.80, SD=1.190).

Table 3: Perception of qualification group towards Koha-ILS: Qualification-wise data and one-way ANOVA test

No	Statements	BS LIS	MLIS	MS/MPhil	Ph.D.	F value	Sig
		N=49	N=112	N=52	N=9		
		M	M	M	M		
		(SD)	(SD)	(SD)	(SD)		
1.	Our Library Services are impacted by Koha software	3.55 1.430	3.09 1.373	3.25 1.426	3.56 1.590	1.377	.251
2.	Charging and discharging of books are made easy by the use of Koha	3.80 1.040	3.39 1.102	3.56 1.074	3.44 1.509	1.561	.200
3.	Libraries have reached the next level because of Koha	3.76 1.199	3.36 1.154	3.25 1.082	3.11 1.269	2.080	.104
4.	Koha makes the acquisition system for smaller libraries simple	3.49 1.063	3.28 1.109	3.21 .997	3.11 1.364	.724	.539
5.	Koha also makes the union catalogue facility available	3.41 1.135	3.15 1.084	3.23 1.059	2.33 1.414	2.514	.059
6.	Koha makes me satisfied while carrying out library services	3.47 1.063	3.18 .942	3.23 1.231	3.00 1.323	1.046	.373
7.	I would recommend Koha to other libraries	3.43 1.323	3.06 1.051	3.23 1.165	3.11 1.364	1.186	.316
8.	I find Koha dependable	3.43 1.190	3.22 1.074	3.15 .937	3.67 1.225	1.055	.369
9.	Koha greatly increases job productivity	3.65 1.128	3.17 1.073	3.19 1.030	3.33 1.323	2.430	.066
10.	Every function of an integrated library management software can	3.80 1.190	3.10 1.115	3.33 1.004	3.11 1.167	4.595	.004
11.	Koha software is user-friendly	3.57 1.061	3.13 1.027	3.25 1.153	3.00 1.225	2.067	.106
12.	For efficient library services, Koha is consistent	3.63 1.220	3.15 1.006	3.35 1.101	3.11 1.364	2.319	.076

Table 4 presents the comparison of male (n=139) and female (n=83) librarians' awareness of Koha-ILS across different aspects, with significant variation in many cases. Male librarians mostly noted that Koha software is more friendly than females, which denotes the highest mean differences in the given

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statements, for example," Koha-ILS is flexible for modification" (M=3.53 vs M=2.77, Sig=.000, F=6.135), next "Koha automates many routine library tasks" (M=3.41 vs M=2.83, Sig=.000, F=4.135). In the table, significant variations were also found in cataloguing skills, web-based interface, cost-effectiveness, and built-in tools, indicating that males rated these aspects as more dominant. In contrast, the variations were less stressed for statements on multilingual backing (M=3.36 vs M=3.11, Sig=.069) and scalability (M=3.43 vs M=3.10, Sig=.022). Throughout, male librarians consistently perceived Koha-ILS as a deeper, more effective, and friendlier user interface than female librarians did.

Table 4: Perception of Librarians towards Koha-ILS: Data distribution based on male and female with t-test

No	Statements	Male Librarians (n=139)		Female Librarians (n=83)		t-test sig. 2-tailed	F test value
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
1.	Koha-ILS is flexible for modifications.	3.53	1.426	2.77	1.253	.000	6.135
2.	Koha eliminates licensing fees, reducing the overall cost of implementing	3.69	1.191	3.24	.878	.001*	15.656
3.	Koha's provide web-based interface enables users to access the system from any internet	3.66	1.183	2.99	.994	.000*	9.130
4.	Koha offers robust cataloguing capabilities	3.49	1.151	2.99	.876	.000*	27.858
5.	Koha automates many routine library tasks, such as circulation, acquisitions, and catalogue maintenance	3.41	1.128	2.83	.998	.000*	4.668
6.	Koha supports integration with interlibrary loan services	3.40	1.153	2.99	.819	.002*	30.292
7.	Koha provides built-in reporting tools and analytics features	3.32	1.251	2.96	.943	.018*	22.122
8.	Koha offers multilingual support in regional languages	3.36	1.171	3.11	.884	.069	19.901
9.	Koha benefits from a vibrant community of developers, librarians, and users who contribute to its ongoing development	3.45	1.149	3.02	.950	.003*	12.854
10.	Koha is scalable and capable of supporting libraries of all sizes	3.43	1.234	3.10	.919	.022*	23.146
11.	Koha training programs and workshops can be organized locally	3.48	1.132	2.87	.866	.000*	15.805
12.	Koha supports interlibrary loan (ILL) integration	3.44	1.155	3.07	.973	.012*	9.797
13.	Koha can be localized to support Urdu or other regional languages	3.53	1.426	2.77	1.253	.000*	6.135

Table 5 presents the comparison of male and female librarians' perceptions towards challenges related to Library operations. According to the survey, Male(n=139) librarians consistently noted all challenges as

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more significant than female (n=83), which denotes statistical significance variations in most cases like "Financial Problems" (M=3.69 vs M=3.24 Sig=.001, F=15.656), "Lack of professional staff" (M=3.66 vs. M=2.99, Sig=.000, F=9.130) "Inadequate in-house expertise" (M=3.49 vs. M=2.99, Sig=.000, F=27.858) and "poor infrastructure" (M=3.40 vs. M=2.99, Sig=.002, F=30.292) in these statements we noted the highest disparities and notable variations. However, in some cases, both groups agreed on the significance, like "lack of interest in Higher Authority" (M=3.32 vs M =2.96, Sig=.018, F=22.122) and "High cost of maintenance" (M=3.36 vs M=3.11, Sig=.069, F=19.901).

Table 5: Barriers and Challenges in KOHA Software: Data distribution based on male and female with t-test

No	Statements	Male Librarians (n=139)		Female Librarians (n=83)		t-test sig. 2-tailed	F test value
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
1.	Financial Problems	3.69	1.191	3.24	.878	.001	15.656
2.	Lack of Professional Staff	3.66	1.183	2.99	.994	.000	9.130
3.	In-adequate in-house expert	3.49	1.151	2.99	.876	.000	27.858
4.	Constantly new versions	3.41	1.128	2.83	.998	.000	4.668
5.	Poor Infrastructure	3.40	1.153	2.99	.819	.002	30.292
6.	Lack of Interest in Higher Authority	3.32	1.251	2.96	.943	.018	22.122
7.	High-cost of maintenance	3.36	1.171	3.11	.884	.069	19.901

Discussion

The present research achieved three objectives. The first objective was "to explore librarians' perceptions regarding the adoption and usability of Koha-ILS in academic libraries across Pakistan". The finding of this objective is based on twelve constructs, and all constructs were measured through a five-point Likert scale formula, like 1= Strongly Agree and 5= Strongly Disagree. The finding of this objective corroborates the finding of (Mohideen et al. (2019), who conducted a survey in five universities in Malaysia and found that the use of KOHA in academic libraries has favourably impacted KOHA. The result of this objective also aligns with the study by Asim & Mairaj (2019), who used the same scale for data collection in Punjab universities in Pakistan. The study's findings indicate that perceptions of librarians vary across regions. The study further discovered that librarians with strong IT Skills perceive KOHA as the best option for their libraries. The finding also endorsed the study of Salma & Mini Devi (2019), who conducted a survey in university libraries of Kerala state and found that librarians in Kerala perceive KOHA as one of the best Open-Source Software with few limitations like technical issues, Operating system, and advanced knowledge of librarians in Information technology. In light of this paper's findings, the study provides a foundation for future research to explore librarians' perspectives in Pakistan using more systematic methods.

The second objective of the present paper is "To evaluate the efficiency and effectiveness of Koha-ILS in enhancing library operations and services in academic libraries in Pakistan.

The findings of this objective are similar to the study of Jabeen (2024), who conducted a study among academic librarians in Islamabad and found that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and facilitating conditions positively influenced the intention to adopt Koha. The study further found that KOHA is more efficient than other proprietary software. However, librarians in Pakistan still need to be fully aware of their efficiency. The finding is also relevant to the study by Kumar V & Jasimudeen (2012), who found that the deployment of KOHA in reputed libraries in India has given new

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professionals sufficient exposure to KOHA, which they did not use in their academic libraries earlier. The findings also corroborate the research of Salma & Mini Devi (2019), who found that the majority of librarians have shifted their services from proprietary software to free and open-source software such as KOHA for its efficiency. Overall, the objective was to determine whether the majority of librarians in Pakistan consider KOHA an efficient software for their academic libraries.

The third objective of this research is “to identify and analyze the challenges faced by librarians during the implementation and ongoing use of Koha-ILS in academic libraries in Pakistan”. The findings show that librarians in Pakistan face difficulties when implementing KOHA for automation. These findings are similar to those of Alikoba & Lwanga (2019), who conducted a study in Uganda and found that the significant challenges librarians face include a need for more technical staff, advanced operating systems, and staff training. Similarly, their study (Asim & Mairaj, 2019) also highlighted that librarian in Punjab universities reported that a lack of knowledge, the Linux operating system, a shortage of skilled workforce, and slow internet speed are a few hurdles in implementing them in their respective libraries. Jabeen (2024) highlighted that the significance of information and communication technology (ICT) skills and the need for IT support staff are among the hurdles librarians in Pakistan face that hamper the utilization of KOHA software.

Similarly, in their study, Hussain and Rafiq (2023) found that trained personnel, power supply, stakeholder inattention, and inadequate technical equipment are among the obstacles to implementing KOHA and other open-source software. The result of this study also concordance with the study of Choi and Pruett (2019), who conducted a quantitative study in the USA and found that the adoption rate of KOHA is still slow and needs to be faster for many reasons inadequate funds, digital resilience of librarians, lack of technical equipment and interest of stakeholders are few problems faced by the librarians.

Conclusion

Koha is a state-of-the-art library helpful for all kinds of libraries, whether public or academic. Developed countries like the USA, UK, and Germany have deployed costly software in their respective libraries. On the other hand, libraries in developing countries are facing numerous challenges, such as a need for additional funding, technical staff, new operating systems, and more. Koha is one of the latest open-source software programs that supports multilingualism for developing countries and provides free, open-source code. The present study finds that developing countries such as Pakistan should fully utilise the Koha-Integrated library system, with appropriate changes. The study also shows that Koha possesses all the required functions/features as other costly software; however, challenges such as a lack of technical skills among library staff, the Linux operating system, and approval from organizational stakeholders may impede the adoption of Koha in academic libraries. The present study highlights academic librarians' perceptions of Koha software, its efficiency, and the challenges they face. By overcoming these obstacles, librarians in Pakistan can fully leverage Koha's quality in their academic settings. Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations are made:

Recommendations

1. The findings indicate that Koha-ILS varies significantly by gender and region. It is necessary to initiate capacity-building and continuous professional development for professionals with limited expertise in Koha. These training and workshops will boost their expertise in Koha administration, reporting tools, cataloguing standards, and system customization, thereby enhancing librarians' technical competence and confidence.

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2. The study reveals differences in awareness and perceptions of Koha-ILS, particularly among female librarians and those living in underrepresented regions of Pakistan. Librarians must initiate orientation programs at the institutional and provincial levels to support female librarians and enhance their understanding of Koha's functionalities.
3. The findings indicate that a lack of interest from higher authorities and financial constraints emerged as a significant barrier. The Higher Education Commission, the Ministry of Education, and the organization's stakeholders should formally recognize Koha-ILS as a strategic digital infrastructure in Pakistan. For this, they should allocate a dedicated budget and develop ICT policies at the institutional level to ensure smoother implementation and sustainability.
4. The findings reveal that poor infrastructure and limited technical support are significant challenges in public universities and in remote regions such as Baluchistan and Gilgit Baltistan. Hence, it is recommended that organizations strengthen their technical infrastructure and IT support for their libraries, upgrading hardware and ensuring reliable internet connectivity, and collaborating with institutional IT departments to overcome infrastructure issues and enhance technical support for Koha-ILS.
5. Since Koha-ILS holds a strong global and local open-source community. It is recommended that academic librarians in Pakistan establish national and regional Koha user groups, as collaborative networks will further enhance knowledge sharing for joint training sessions, troubleshooting, and localized solutions.
6. Librarians with BS and Master degree show relatively higher mean score on certain Koha-related functions. It is necessary for LIS educational institutions to integrate Koha competencies into LIS curricula. LIS schools in Pakistan should also embed training programs for their graduate at the academic level for better preparation in future.
7. Academic librarians should adopt mixed methods, longitudinal approaches to assess the long-term impact of Koha-ILS on service quality, organizational performance, and user satisfaction across different regions of Pakistan. This would further enrich their understanding towards Koha adoption in future.

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References:

- Abid, H. (2021). Uses of block chain technologies in library services. *Library Hi Tech News*, 38(8), 9-11.
- Ahmad, S., Ibrahim, M., Ahmad, S., & Hussain, A. (2024). The Adoption of Open-Source software is in Libraries in Digital Era: A Case Study of Pakistan. *Journal of Information Management and Practices*, 4(1).
- Ahmedani, A. A., Shahzad, K., Siddique, R., & Khan, S. (2022). Comparative Study for Assessment of Koha and SLIMS Features in Public Sector College Libraries of Sindh.
- Asim, M., & Mairaj, M. I. (2019). Librarians' perceptions about adoption and uses of the Koha integrated library software in Punjab, Pakistan. *The Electronic Library*, 37(4), 624-635.
- Chauhan, K. (2018). Evaluation in use of KOHA Library Management Software in OPJGU, Sonipat. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, 2070.
- Darko-Ampem, K. (2017). Implementing Koha at Regent University College, Ghana: A case study of options, opportunities and challenges. *Library and Information Research*, 41(124), 85-109.
- House, M. D. (2016). Implementing the open-source Koha-ILS at the Deutsche Schule Charlotte. *Digital Library Perspectives*, 32(4), 253-269.
- Hussain, A. (2024). Unlocking the potential of ChatGPT in academic libraries. *IP Indian Journal of Library Science and Information Technology*, 9(2), 88-97. <https://doi.org/10.18231/j.ijlsit.2024.015>
- Hussain, A. (2020). Cutting edge: technology's impact on library services. In *Innovations in the designing and marketing of information services* (pp. 16-27). IGI Global.
- Hussain, A. (2020). Industrial revolution 4.0: implication to libraries and librarians. *Library hi tech news*, 37(1), 1-5.
- Hussain, A., & Jan, S. U. (2018). Awareness of web 2.0 technology in the academic libraries: an Islamabad perspective. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1-13.
- Hussain, A. (2021). Strategy of libraries and librarians during COVID-19. *The International Journal of Law, Humanities & Social Science*, 5(1), 40-49.
- Hussain, A. (2022). Review of augmented reality in academic and research libraries. *Library Hi Tech News*, 39(9), 23-25.
- Hussain, A. (2022). Use of WhatsApp technology in library services: case study of national defence university library, Islamabad, Pakistan. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1-11.
- Hussain, A. (2023). Use of geographical information system (GIS) application in public libraries. *Library Hi Tech News*, (ahead-of-
- Hussain, A., & Jan, S. U. (2018). User perception on Electronic resources and services in National Defense University Library Islamabad, Pakistan. *Pakistan Library & Information Science Journal*, 49(3), 58-68.
- Hussain, A., & Rafiq, M. (2023). Perceptions of Academic Librarians toward Open-Source Library System (OSLS): Case Study of Pakistan. *Science & Technology Libraries*, 1-11.
- Hussain, A., & Richardson, J. (2024). Awareness of Pakistani academic librarians towards communication skills: barriers and benefits. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*.
- Hussain, A., & Shahid, R. (2022). Impact of big data on library services: prospect and challenges. *Library Hi Tech News*, 000-000.
- Hussain, A. (2025). Redefining libraries in 21st Century: Transformative roles for Bridging research, education, technology and society. National Book Foundation, 1-210.
- Ismail, M., Hussain, A., Gul, S., & Sajid, I. A. (2022). Library Anxiety among Undergraduate Students: A case study of faculty of Management Science, University of Peshawar. *Library Philosophy & Practice*.
- Keast, D. (2011). A survey of Koha in Australian special libraries: open source brings new opportunities to the outback. *OCLC Systems & Services: International digital library perspectives*, 27(1), 23-39.

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- Kumar V, V., & Jasimudeen, S. (2012). Adoption and user perceptions of Koha library management system in India.
- Macan, B., Vanesa Fernandez, G., & Stojanovski, J. (2013). Open source solutions for libraries: ABCD vs Koha. *Program*, 47(2), 136-154.
- Mahmood, K. (1996). Library and information services in Pakistan: A review of articles published in foreign journals. *The International Information & Library Review*, 28(4), 383-405.
- Mahmood, K. (1999). The development of computerised library services in Pakistan: A review of the literature. *Asian Libraries*, 8(9), 307-328.
- Mahmood Malik, K. (1996). The status of library automation in Pakistan. *Library Review*, 45(6), 36-42.
- Mairaj, M. I., & El-Hadi, W. M. (2012). Applications of information and communication technologies in libraries in Pakistan. *Journal of the Medical Library Association: JMLA*, 100(3), 218.
- Makori, E. O., & Osebe, N. M. (2016). Koha enterprise resource planning system and its potential impact on information management organizations. *Library Hi Tech News*, 33(4), 17-23.
- Masrek, M. N., & Hussein, A. (2021). Intention to adopt mobile applications services: A study among Pakistani academic librarians. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 15(3), 38-54.
- Omeluzor, S. U., Adara, O., Ezinwayi, M., Bamidele, A. I., & Umahi, F. O. (2012). Implementation of Koha integrated library management software (ILMS): the Babcock University experience. *Canadian Social Science*, 8(4), 211-221.